

A Jain Sculptures of Badami

Dr. M N. Bennur¹, Dr. CN. Kologudde²

¹Head Dept. Of History, S T C Arts and Commerce College Banahatti - Karnataka

² Asst. Professor, Dept. of History and Arch. Rani Channamma University Belagavi. Karnatak

Corresponding Author: Dr. M N. Bennur

Abstract:

Badami is one of the ancient Jain centre of ancient Karnataka. In this centre there were remarkable heritage Jain centre in Badami. Badami was a capital city of Chalukya's of Badami, dedicated to caves of Hindu Gods and Jain Tirthankaras were built by Chalukya rulers. There are four cave temples in the fort of Badami. The sculptures of Adinath, Parshwanath, Mahaveer, Bahubali, Goutham Swami and 24 tirthankara's were carved on the wall of forth Jain Cave, which was located on the hillocks opposite to the fort. Pattadakallu is a World Heritage Site, recognised by UNESCO. It had only one Jain Narayan Temple. Badami Caves and Jain Basadi's were in the style of architecture of Chalukya's of Badami.

Key Words: Pilaster – A rectangular column, Aisle – A passage between rows of seats in building, Mukamantap – Front open wall, Garbhagriha – Sanctum, Knitting – Method by which yarn is manipulated to create a textile, Viman – Peak.

Introduction:

The city of Badami in Northern Karnataka, formerly known as Vatapi, was the capital of one of the greatest and most enduring dynasties in Southern India and was also most popular historical places in southern India. It was the regal capital of the Badami Chalukyas from AD 540 to 757. It is famous for its rock cut structural temples. It is located in a ravine at the foot of a rugged, red sandstone outcrop that surrounds Agastyalake. Badami has been selected as one of the heritage cities of Government of India and the historical study of Badami is an interesting concept. Jain Basadi's and sculptures which had given shelter to the Jain Muni's.

Badami Jain Cave:

The architectural structure constructed through the rock of stones is caves. The caves constructed by Badami Chalukyas became temples. The 4 caves in badami were carved on the north side of the southern hills. As a result of that all the caves are more or less situated on northwards. Thus at any time of year the sun light directly cannot enter into the caves. Under the hills of these caves a spacious Agasthya thirtha exists. These caves are popularly known as Menabasti or Menabasadi. Of these the one is of Shaiva and other two are of Vaishnav and Jain's caves. It is very small cave. These made it very convenient to understand the impact of the architecture of the ancient Karnataka over the architectures built by Badami Chalukyas and the caves of their neighbouring pallavas¹.

Architecture of IV Cave of Badami:

The forth cave belongs to Jain community. Probably it was constructed during the period of Mangalash. It is smaller as the first and second caves. The cave is 15 feet high; it is supported by 6 pillars, each measuring 2.5 square feet. Each column and pilaster is carved with wide, deep basis crowned with capitals that are partly hidden by bracket on

three sides. The sculptures of Parshwanath and Gommateshwar on the walls of varanda were made during the rule of Chalukyas. The sculptures of tirthankar on the walls of mahamantap were of 12th century. The anatomy of these sculptures itself proves it².

A Corridor, a pillar of the aisle, and a Sanctum are there in first three caves temple. Pillar of aisle are not existed in Jain cave. However, there is a square Mantap without pillars. All the caves are of same shape. Pillars of mukamantap supposed to standing on back of the sleeping lion. The basement of the pillar is in square structure, Top is designed cover. It has been decorated half-structured medals. The pillars and their caps were square in size. They are stretched in wave shapes. The external part of the pillars is shaped like horns of the lions. Which are supportive to the caves³. On the sanctum of cave, flower designs, diamond shapes, tube shapes, and tube shaped Aquarius, tube shaped fine, circular caps, and square house frames are carved. Lower part of the doors, there are dwarapalakas. Around the whole design there are three large joints, of which five small temples are curved in the forms of lines and meetings⁴. It's quite commonly found on the top of the pillars, the imaginative figures of Medals, Mathangankra, Hamsa, Angles, Padma, Patralatha, Peacock, Semi human and semi bird in Badami Caves. These shapes are used for knitting – bars and Pallava caves⁵.

The Sculptures of IV Cave of Badami:

Parshwanath Sculpture:

This sculpture faced towards southern with a height of 86 cm. and width of 31c.m. A five-headed snake halos on its top. Beside the statue, there are attractive sculptures of angles. There is a picture of kamtopsarga on the west walls in parshwanath sculpture. The yaksha Dharanendra stood under the five-headed snake in bare body. There incomplete sculptures in both the sides of the

parshwanath statue. On the right side of the parshwanath, padmavathi yakshi, who had held a diamond umbrella just above the heads of snake. It seems on the top of the parshwanath, kamata a birth enemy of parshwanatha, throwing rock from his hands. Defeated kamata who was sitting with surrender mode on the legs of the Parshwanatha ⁶.

Mahaveera Sculpture:

The Mahaveera sculptures are designed on the East and West walls with about 2 mtrs height. Just below the Mahavira sculpture, a carve of Mathanga, a yaksha, sitting on elephant and Siddayini a yakshini, sitting under a tree are shown ⁷. A statue of tirthankara on the top of the simha peeta with a height of 28cms and width of 73 cms is situated in garbhagraha of caves. Due to unavailability in the inscriptions of thirthankar it is not possible to tell the accurate name of Basadi.

Bahubali Sculpture:

There is a Bahubali sculpture on the east walls of mukhmantap. It is imagined that this **sculpture** is an ancient sculpture in Karnataka. Bahubali stood barely in Kayotsarga mudra. His hair is knotted. The limbs of his body are surrounded by creepers of various flowers. It is shown that the king cobras coming out of anthills, which are grown under his legs. Vidhyadhari's are untying the creepers that are surrounded from his limbs and the other two vidhyadhari's are sitting with saluting. Only the statue of Bahubali is completed but the statue of vidhyadhari is incomplete and its height is 34cms only ⁸.

Sculptors:

Very few of these sculptors will remind us the tradition of 3rd cave of Badami. There many names of sculptors in this cave atmosphere, of which Kantimatja Kannu, **Pelamatja**, Singamatja, Harike, Bavaswami Arya, Udagra, Kesava, Pajjana, Vijamma, Prasanna Buddi, Arikke, Bhadukke, Sirigereya, Kolimajja, Kadreswami, Shrigerey, Margaj, Shrinidhi Dev, Anattamajja and so many ⁹.

Conclusion:

Jain religion was named as an oldest religion in global religions and it has an ancient chronicler. We can say that, Jain religion was lives from several years with having good relation with other religions. Caves, Basadi's and sculptures of Badami. In this centre, we can find lot of Parshwanath and Mahaveer Sculptures. This Jain religion helped to became a oldest heritage Jain centres. This article is prepared with the help of sources found and survey made by us.

Foot notes:

1. Dr. Gopal.R. : The History and Epigraphy of Bagalakot district -Directorate of Archaeology and Museum Exhibition Complex, Mysore.2011.P-242

2. Dr. Rajashekhar.S: Temple architecture of Karnataka- page-296-297
3. Iranna.KP: Badami Chalukyar Sanskrutika Parampare-Manu Sahitya Prakashan Dharwad, P-121
4. Dr. Rajashekhar.S: Temple architecture of Karnataka- page-297-98
5. Dr.Rajashekkrappa. B: P-300
6. Ibid-302
7. Prop . Shrinivas VPadagar : Badami Chalukyara Shashanagalu, Vastu Mattu Shilpakale (Kannada Medium) Karnataka Itihas Samshodhan Mandal Dharwad, 2007-08 P-69
8. Dr. Shilakant . Pattar : A Culural Study Of Badami - Prasaraanga – K U Hampi. (KannadaMedium) 2000 P-232.
9. Prop . Shrinivas VPadagar : Badami Chalukyara Shashanagalu, Vastu Mattu Shilpakale (Kannada Medium) Karnataka Itihas Samshodhan Mandal Dharwad, 2007-08 P-69.